

IN SITU OBSERVATION OF DELAMINATION FRACTURE TEST IN GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE DURING MODE II LOADING INSIDE A SEM

Y. Q. SUN, T. L. ANDERSON* and J. TIAN

(Northwest Institute of Textile Sci. & Tech. 710048, Xian, China)

* (Texas A & M University, College Station, TX 77843, U. S. A.)

ABSTRACT

A graphite fiber reinforced resin composite was mode II loaded inside a SEM. The entire fracture process including the microscopic change of a crack tip damage zone with load increasing was observed, recorded and analysed. Results show that under a mode II loading, the entire fracture process of a laminate experienced bamboo corrugated band forming, microcrack initiating, stretching, growing, rotating and coalescing, the precrack extending, and unstable crack propagating; the size of the damage zone and microcrack number in the zone increased with load until the maximum load reached.

Keywords: delamination, graphite/epoxy composite, microcrack, crack tip damage zone

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials have increasingly become important in the field of materials and structures. The more and more applications have been found in engineering, especially in aircraft and spacecraft structures. This is mainly attributed to their high strength to weight and stiffness to weight ratios and the opportunity to tailor material properties by the control of fiber and matrix composition and fiber orientation through processing procedure.

Delamination has been recognized as one of the major failure modes which has limited the extensive use of graphite fiber reinforced resin composites in some structure applications. Considerable effort has been made to improve the delamination fracture toughness [1-4]. In order to gain insight into micromechanism of delamination, several investigators have conducted the in situ studies in a SEM [5,6,7]. With a new loading system which consists of a tensile stage, a load cell and a signal processor, the current

investigation attempts to go further into the in-situ studies. Special attention was focused on the entire fracture process, the behavior of a crack tip damage zone which includes the size and shape of a damage zone, and the nucleation, growth, rotation of microcrack in the zone under different load levels

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2. 1. Material and specimen preparation

The material used in this study was a unidirectional graphite/epoxy laminate AS4/3502 supplied by Hercules Corporation. The graphite fiber AS4 has an average tensile strength of 520 ksi, and the epoxy 3502, a highly crosslinked resin, was utilized as matrix. Therefore, this composite has a higher glass transition temperature ($T_g = 213^\circ\text{C}$) and is relatively brittle.

Miniature DCB specimens are rectangular plates (30mm long, 5mm wide and 1 mm thick) with fibers parallel to the longitudinal axis. The specimens were cut from a eight ply laminate using a diamond blade cutter. Then they were precracked by razor blade under a stereomicroscope. The specimen surfaces to be observed were ground with sand paper and polished with alumina powder to a 0.3 micron finish on an automatic polisher, cleaned ultrasonically first in a soap-distilled water solution and then with distilled water only, dried in an oven, and finally sputter coated with approximate 100 angstrom of a gold-palladium alloy.

2. 2. Test inside a SEM

The fracture test was performed on a JEOL-T330A scanning electron microscope using a tensile stage equipped with a load cell and a signal processor supplied by Fulam Inc. Therefore, the loads applied to the specimen can be monitored and recorded at any moment during the test. The mode I loading condition was accomplished using a specially designed three point bend fixture.

Before loading a specimen, the area ahead of a precrack tip was focused on and a series of pictures was taken as a reference in order to make comparison afterward. Then the specimen was loaded inside column of the SEM by using the loading rod outside the column which connected to the tensile stage. Special care had to be taken to avoid unexpected unstable crack propagation which is apt to occur because of the brittle behavior of this material. The specimen was loaded slowly and incrementally until the maximum load reached and the microcracks initiated. Several series of pictures of damaged zone of the crack tip were taken at each load level during the loading process.

2. 3. Image Analysis

An image processing system (IPS) manufactured by Kontron was used to analyse the images of pictures taken during the test. Through direct measuring the SEM micrographs the damage zone size and the microcrack number corresponding to the given load level were obtained.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SEM micrographs in Fig. 1 show the area ahead of a crack tip under different test phase. Before loading, as seen in Fig. 1(a), a precrack tip is seen to locate in the resin rich zone between the fibers and to be very close to the fiber beneath it, as shown by an arrow.

During the loading, as shown in Fig. 1(b) through (f), different microfeatures corresponding to given load levels appeared in the area ahead of the crack tip. At the first phase of loading, the crack tip was blunted and the crack tip opening distance increased. Then with the load increasing, some microfeature called white bamboo corrugated lines which are about 4 to 5 μm in length and about 0.5 μm in width were formed in the direction approximate 45° relative to the crack plane. These corrugated lines formed a corrugated line band. As the load was increased further, the microcracks initiated on the corrugated band in the direction perpendicular to the white corrugated lines. The microscopic appearance of a typical white bamboo corrugated line band can be seen in Fig. 2.

With the load increasing further more, the microcracks stretched, grew, and simultaneously the axis of microcracks rotated gradually, which corresponded to the shear stress applied. Then the microcracks coalesced, finally the crack tip advanced. The entire fracture process is schematic in Fig. 3.

3. 1. Damage Zone Size and Shape

From the pictures shown in Fig. 4, it can be seen that under a Mode II loading, a long and slender damage zone is produced in a resin rich zone between fibers. As the load was increased the damage zone size was increased until the maximum load was reached. The length of the damage zone measured here is 300 μm , and the widths are ranged from 11 μm at the crack tip to 2 μm at the end of the damage zone.

The shape of the crack tip damage zone here appears to be somewhat similar to the

crack tip plastic zone anticipated by Dugdale approach. The difference is obvious; the former is much longer than the latter. Besides the different loading mode, there are other reasons for this. One is the fibre restriction which restrained the damage zone from developing in the vertical direction and made it expand easily along the direction parallel to the fibers. Another reason which may be more essential comes from the inherent nature of the material. The brittle matrix, epoxy 3502, imparts the composite a lower fracture toughness and can only allow a limited damage zone to be developed before a unstable crack propagation occurs .

3. 2. Microcrack formation under different loads

Fig. 5 relates the microcrack number in the damage zone to the load applied. At the first phase of loading, there was not microcrack formed. As the load was reached to a certain level, a few microcracks appeared. With the load increasing further, the microcracks initiated previously began to grow. Simultaneously, more and more new microcracks initiated consequently in the white bamboo corrugated line band of the damage zone. In this way, the microcrack zone expanded from the left to the right until a maximum load was reached. Then, either increasing the load little more or keeping enough duration of loading will give rise to the main crack tip advance .

It was noted that when new microcracks initiated or the microcracks formed previously grew, a certain amount of load (0.5-1lb) was seen to be dropped. This is because both the initiation and growth of microcracks are energy consuming processes which cause the stress relaxing and partial unloading.

3. 3. Microcrack rotation during loading

Another observation during loading is microcrack rotation. At the beginning of microcracks initiating, the orientation of their major axis was approximate 135° relative to fiber direction. With load increasing the axis of the cracks rotated gradually from 135° to 90° , as shown in Fig. 1 and 3. When the angle reached about 90° the main crack extension occurred.

Under a approximately identical load level, the orientation of a microcrack depended generally upon the location of the crack, i. e, the distance from the crack tip. If the material was microscopically homogeneous, the closer to the tip the microcrack, the larger the amount of rotation. On the area which was very close to the main crack tip the angle was about 90° , while in the region which located near to another end of the damage zone, the angle still was original. In other word, if the focus was removed

from the far end of the damage zone to the main crack tip, the orientation of microcrack gradually increased from 135° to 90°.

From above, two points may be made. One is that the orientation of microcrack depends not only upon the load level, but also upon the location of a microcrack in the zone. Another is that it seems to exist a critical orientation of microcrack, i. e., the angle between microcrack and fiber. It seems that the angle has a critical value 90° which may also be called a maximum value. When a main crack tip extended further through microcrack coalescing, the angle almost always reached 90° in this investigation.

4. SUMMARY

1. Under a Mode II loading, a entire delamination fracture process consists of crack tip blunting, white bamboo corrugated band forming, initiation, stretching, growing, rotating and coalescing of microcracks, and a main crack advance if a precrack tip locates in a resin rich zone.
2. The crack tip damage zone size and the microcrack number in the damage zone increase with load until a maximum load is reached.
3. During loading the microcracks rotated gradually from the original approximate 135° to 90°. The 90° seems to be a critical value for a precrack to propagate.

Acknowledgements

The project was supported by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research. The authors also wish to acknowledge the technical support given by the Electron Microscopy Center of Texas A & M University.

References

1. Bascom, W. D. , Ting, R. Y. , Moulton, R. J. , Riew, C. K. and Siebert, A. R. , J. Mater. Sci. ,16,1981,pp2657.
2. Manzione, L. T. and Gillham, J. K. , J. Appl. polym. Sci. 26,1981, PP907
3. Chakachery, E. A. and Bradley, W. L. , Polym. Engr. and Sci. 27, 1987, PP33.
4. Smith, B. W. and Grove, R. A. , "Determination of Crack Propagation Directions in Graphite/Epoxy Structures," Fractography of Modern Engineering Materials : Composites and Metals, ASTM STP 948, 1987, pp. 154—173
5. Hibbs, M. F. and Bradley, W. L. , "Correlations Between Micromechanical Fail-

ure Processes and the Delamination Toughness of Graphite/Epoxy Systems,” *Fractography of Modern Engineering Materials: Composites and Metals*, ASTM STP 948, 1987, PP. 68—97

6. Chakachery, E. A. , PhD Dissertation , Texas A & M University, May ,1989
7. Corleto, C. R. , PhD Dissertation, Texas A & M University ,1991.

Fig. 1. In situ delamination of AS4/3502 under mode II loading

- (a) Before loading
- (b) Crack tip blunting, and white bamboo corrugated band formation
- (c), (d) and (e) Microcrack initiation, growth and rotation
- (f) Microcrack Coalescence and precrack advance

Fig. 2. Microscopic appearance of a typical white bamboo corrugated band.

Fig. 3. Schematic of a entire mode II in situ delamination fracture process. (a) through (f) here corresponding to the (a) through (f) in the Fig. 1

Fig. 4. Crack tip damage zone.

Fig. 5. Relation between the number of accumulated microcrack and load.